

ECONOMICS OF MARKETING OF LATE KHARIF ONION IN NASHIK DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

Onion is a commercial crop in India. India is currently the world's largest producer of onion followed by China. A crucial factor from a farmer's perspective is onion marketing. Despite increased production, price swings, high marketing cost and significant losses at various points during the marketing process frequently prevent growers from receiving a fair price. Considering importance present study was undertaken for the year 2023-24 with 45 sample cultivators comprising of 15 small, 15 medium and 15 large cultivators from Niphad and Yeola tahsils of Nashik district of Maharashtra. 5 wholesalers and retailers respectively. The study identified a predominant marketing channel of Producer → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer, with transport costs being a major expense. Marketing margins and price spreads varied by grade wise, major marketing margin was observed for retailer with Grade II onions providing the highest producer share in consumer rupees i.e. 54.48 per cent for late kharif.

Key-words- Onion, Marketing cost, Late kharif, Price spread, Nashik

Introduction

In recent years, onions have been employed both for domestic consumption and for export. The price of onions can change dramatically on domestic markets, necessitating government involvement in the form of importing onion in response to market conditions when price go high. The onion has significantly helped earn significant foreign currency. A comprehensive and diversified marketing network enables the farmer to bring the produce to the market most efficiently and timely. It reduces post-harvest losses, enhances competition and allows price discovery. With the increase in marketable surplus, it has become all the more essential to provide the farming community with better marketing facilities. Delays in farmers accessing formal institutions, including for government procurement at the Agricultural Produce Market Committee (APMC), enhance reliance on intermediaries.

Material and Methods

The study was based on primary data of year 2023-24 collected from 45 cultivators from Niphad and Yeola tehsil of Nashik district of Maharashtra. The onion growers were categorized into three size groups on the basis of operational land holding as below,

1. Small groups: below 1.0 hectare
2. Medium groups: 1.0 – 2.0 hectare
3. Large groups: above 2.01 hectare.

Marketing Cost, Marketing margin, Price spread and Producers share in consumer rupees were analysed using below given formulas,

Marketing costs

$$C = C_p + C_{m1} + C_{m2} + \dots + C_{mn}$$

Where,

C = Total Cost of Marketing of commodity

C_p = Cost paid by the producer from the time of Produce leaves the farm till he sells it.

C_{m1} = Cost incurred by ith middleman in the process of Buying and selling the product.

Marketing margin

$$MT = \sum (S_i - P_i) / Q_i$$

Where,

MT = Total marketing margin

Table 1: Marketing cost for late kharif onion producer (₹/qtl.)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III
1	Labour Charges	27.43 (33.07)	27.60 (33.20)	27.27 (32.94)
2	Transport Charges	42.97 (51.80)	42.97 (51.70)	42.97 (51.90)
3	Storage Charges	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
4	Hamali	7.25 (8.74)	7.25 (8.72)	7.25 (8.76)
5	Tolai	4.80	4.80	4.80

S_i = Sale value of a product by ith firm

P_i = Purchase value of a product paid by ith firm

Q_i = Quantity of product handled by ith firm

Price spread

$$P_s = C_p - P_f$$

Where,

P_s = Price spread

C_p = Consumer's price

P_f = Price received by farmer

Producer share in consumer rupee

$$\text{Producers share in consumers rupee} = \frac{\text{Price received by producer}}{\text{Price paid by consumer}} \times 100$$

Marketing efficiency

$$E = (O/I) \times 100$$

Where,

E = Marketing efficiency,

O = Price paid by consumer (₹),

I = Marketing cost + Marketing margin of intermediaries (₹).

Results and Discussion

Marketing channels illustrate the pathways through which produce moves from producers to final consumers. In the study area, only one major channel was identified in the marketing process that was Producer → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer, 99.9 per cent cultivators used this channel. Similar kind of results was reported by Barakade (2018), Malaisamy (2021).

3.1 Cost of marketing incurred by late kharif onion producer

The result of marketing has been depicted in **Table 1**. The marketing cost analysis revealed that the primary variations among onion grades were in labour charges, with other components like transport, storage, hamali, tolai and vehicle entry fee remaining consistent. The uniformity in most cost reflected standardized practices in the marketing process, while the variations in labour cost align with the differing handling requirements for different grades of onions. Major portion was of transport charges. Such findings were also reported by Barakade (2018), Vedamurthy *et al* (2020).

		(5.79)	(5.78)	(5.80)
6	Vehicle entry fee	0.50 (0.60)	0.50 (0.60)	0.50 (0.60)
7	Total	82.95 (100.00)	83.11 (100.00)	82.79 (100.00)

Cost of marketing incurred by wholesaler for late kharif onion

In Table 2 the marketing costs for wholesalers handling *late kharif* onion varied slightly by grade. For Grade I onions, the total cost was ₹316.37 per quintal, for Grade II it was ₹309.67 and for Grade III it was ₹297.98.

Table 2: Marketing cost for wholesaler (*late kharif*) (₹/qtl.)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III
1	Labour Charges	40.00 (12.64)	40.00 (12.92)	40.00 (13.42)
2	Loading and Unloading Charges	22.00 (6.95)	22.00 (7.10)	22.00 (7.38)
3	Transport Charges	140.00 (44.25)	140.00 (45.21)	140.00 (46.98)
4	Cost of gunny bag	70.00 (22.13)	70.00 (22.60)	70.00 (23.49)
5	Storage Charge	4.00 (1.26)	3.00 (0.97)	2.00 (0.67)
6	Commission Charges	38.37 (12.13)	32.67 (10.55)	21.98 (7.38)
7	Market Fee	2.00 (0.63)	2.00 (0.65)	2.00 (0.67)
8	Total	316.37 (100.00)	309.67 (100.00)	297.98 (100.00)

Cost of marketing incurred by retailer for late kharif onion

Marketing cost of retailer indicated in Table 3. For Grade I, Grade II and Grade III, the total marketing cost was consistently ₹73.25 per quintal. Major expenses were on transport charges. This result confirms the finding of Kantariya *et al* (2018).

Table 3: Marketing cost for retailer (*late kharif and rabi*) (₹/qtl.)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III
1	Packing material charges	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
2	Transport charges	50.00 (68.26)	50.00 (68.26)	50.00 (68.26)
3	Loading and Unloading	20.00 (27.30)	20.00 (27.30)	20.00 (27.30)
4	Weighing Charges	3.25 (4.44)	3.25 (4.44)	3.25 (4.44)
5	Total	73.25 (100.00)	73.25 (100.00)	73.25 (100.00)

Grade wise marketing cost, marketing margin, marketing efficiency and price spread of late kharif onion

The analysis of marketing costs and margins for *late kharif* onions presented in Table 4. It revealed that for the farmer, the gross prices received per quintal were ₹1278.96 for Grade I which was highest due to its quality, ₹1089.59 for Grade II and ₹732.52 for Grade III.

The marketing costs incurred by the farmer were ₹82.95 for Grade I, ₹83.26 for Grade II and ₹82.81 for Grade III. As a result, the net prices realized by the farmer, after accounted for these costs, were ₹1196.02 for Grade I, ₹1006.32 for Grade II and ₹649.71 for Grade III.

The wholesaler faced marketing costs of ₹316.37 for Grade I, ₹309.67 for Grade II and ₹297.98 for Grade III. When these costs were included, the total prices for the wholesaler amounted to ₹1,595.33, ₹1,399.26 and ₹1,030.50 for Grade I, Grade II and Grade III respectively. The marketing margins for the wholesaler were ₹364.67 for Grade I, ₹80.74 for Grade II and ₹19.50 for Grade III, leading to final prices received by the wholesaler of ₹1,960.00, ₹1,480.00 and

₹1,050.00 for Grade I, Grade II and Grade III, respectively. The marketing costs for the retailer were ₹73.25 for all grades. This resulted in total prices of ₹2,033.25 for Grade I, ₹1,553.25 for Grade II and ₹1,123.25 for Grade III. The marketing margins for the retailer were ₹666.75 for Grade I, ₹446.75 for Grade II and ₹376.75 for Grade III. Between all intermediaries, highest marketing margin was of retailer across all grades. Finally, the consumer paid ₹2700.00 for Grade I, ₹2000.00 for Grade II and ₹1500.00 for Grade III.

The price spread, indicated the difference between the final consumer price and the price received by the farmer, for Grade I highest price spread of ₹ 1,503.98 indicated more marketing cost and marketing margin in marketing Grade I onion. Highest Marketing efficiency of 2.01 was observed in Grade II also highest producer share in consumer rupees of 54.48 was observed, indicated less marketing margin in Grade II onion. These result corroborate with the findings Barakade(2018), Malaisamy(2021), Meena *et al.*(2016)

Table 4: Grade wise Marketing cost, Marketing margin, Marketing efficiency and Price spread of late kharif onion (₹/qtl.)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III
		<i>late kharif</i>	<i>late kharif</i>	<i>late kharif</i>
1	Gross price received by the farmer	1278.96 (47.37)	1089.59 (54.48)	732.52 (48.83)
	i) Marketing cost	82.95	83.26	82.81

		(3.07)	(4.16)	(5.52)
	ii) Net price realized	1196.02 (44.30)	1006.32 (50.32)	649.71 (43.31)
2	Wholesaler			
	i) Price paid	1278.96 (47.37)	1089.59 (54.48)	732.52 (48.83)
	ii) Marketing cost	316.37 (11.72)	309.67 (15.48)	297.98 (19.87)
	Total	1595.33 (59.09)	1399.26 (69.96)	1030.50 (68.70)
	iii) Marketing margin	364.67 (13.51)	80.74 (4.04)	19.50 (1.30)
	iv) Price received	1960.00 (72.59)	1480.00 (74.00)	1050.00 (70.00)
3	Retailer			
	i) Price paid	1960.00 (72.59)	1480.00 (74.00)	1050.00 (70.00)
	ii) Marketing cost	73.25 (2.71)	73.25 (3.66)	73.25 (4.88)
	Total	2033.25 (75.31)	1553.25 (77.66)	1123.25 (74.88)
	iii) Marketing margin	666.75 (24.69)	446.75 (22.34)	376.75 (25.12)
	iv) Price received	2700.00 (100.00)	2000.00 (100.00)	1500.00 (100.00)
4	Consumer			
	i) Price paid	2700.00 (100.00)	2000.00 (100.00)	1500.00 (100.00)
	Price spread	1503.98	993.68	850.29
	Total Marketing Cost	472.57	466.18	454.04
	Total Marketing Margin	1031.42	527.49	396.25
	Marketing Cost + Marketing Margin	1503.98	993.68	850.29
	Marketing Efficiency	1.80	2.01	1.76
	Producer share in Consumer rupees	47.37	54.48	48.83

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total)

Conclusions

Only one marketing channel was found i.e. Producer-Wholesaler-Retailer-Consumer, 99.9 per cent people followed this marketing channel.

Grade wise marketing cost were analysed for *late kharif* which showed that ₹82.95/qtl cost incurred for marketing by producer out of which 52 per cent cost was of transport charges for *late kharif*

Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler varied between ₹297/qtl to ₹316.37/qtl grade wise for *late kharif* and major contributing factor to both was transport charges between 43 to 44 per cent.

Cost incurred by retailer for marketing was 73.25 for *late kharif*. Major cost was of transport of 68.25 per cent.

Price spread i.e. ₹1,503.98 was highest in grade I onion as marketing margin was highest and producer share in consumer rupees was highest in grade II onion which is 54.48 per cent for *late kharif* season as marketing cost and marketing margin was less in grade II onion.

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